

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE EFFECTS OF LAY-UP, STRESS LEVEL, AND STRESS RATIO ON FATIGUE DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT IN GRAPHITE EPOXIES USING RADIOGRAPHY

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SUMMARY

This academic project studied the effects of different variables on damage progression around a hole. The tracked variables included the type of layup and stress ratios/values. In-situ x-ray recorded the extent of damage, mostly longitudinal splitting, as a function of the cycle count. The lay-ups included: $[45/90/-45/0_2/45/0_2/-45/0]_s$, $[\pm 5/65/(\pm 5)_2/-65/\pm 5]_s$, and $[\pm 5/65/(\pm 5)_2/-65/5/65]_s$.

Keywords: non-traditional lay-ups, damage, composites, off-axis plies

INTRODUCTION

This research focused on the fatigue of non-traditional laminates, in which off-axis plies replaced the longitudinal 0° plies of traditional laminates. In all cases, these off-axis plies lead to entirely new laminates without any 0° , 45° , or 90° ply in them. Ideally, a minimal reduction in strength would hopefully be offset by a marked increase in the structure's resistance to crack propagation, or damage tolerance [6]. This is of interest because of extensive use of composites as structural components in aircraft, with multiple holes used for joints and other connections. During the testing phase, each specimen was subsequently monitored for several modes of damage – specifically longitudinal splitting, matrix cracking, and delamination both at the surface (fiber pulloff from off-axis plies) and traditional delamination found near the middle of the stacking sequence. However, the primary damage found during the testing was longitudinal splitting. Damage was measured through the use of in-situ x-ray and a dye penetrant, and recorded as the greatest longitudinal distance between the furthestmost crack tips.

SPECIMENS, EQUIPMENT, PROCEDURES

Specimens

Using a carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg., the specimens were laid up by hand and cured. The three layups included were all 20 ply laminates with the following stacking sequences: $[45/90/-45/0_2/45/0_2/-45/0]_s$, $[\pm 5/65/(\pm 5)_2/-65/\pm 5]_s$, and $[\pm 5/65/(\pm 5)_2/-65/5/65]_s$. Hereafter, these laminates will be referred to by the percentage of certain plies. $[45/90/-45/0_2/45/0_2/-45/0]_s$ will be known as 50/40/10 – the percentage of $0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ$ plies. $[\pm 5/65/(\pm 5)_2/-65/\pm 5]_s$ becomes 80/20 (80% of $\pm 5^\circ$ plies, 20% of $\pm 65^\circ$ plies). $[\pm 5/65/(\pm 5)_2/-65/5/65]_s$ becomes 70/30 (70% of $\pm 5^\circ$ plies, 30% of $\pm 65^\circ$ plies). These laminates are all considered to be “hard” laminates, because the longitudinal stiffness is significantly higher than the transverse stiffness. The specimens were cut into 38.1mm by 304.8mm sections with a 6.35mm hole in the middle of the coupon specimen.

Equipment

A 100kN servo-hydraulic test frame was used to fatigue the composite laminates. The residual strength tests were conducted in a similar 500kN test frame. Both units had computer control with data acquisition capability and strain was measured using a 2.54cm extensometer. The x-ray system had a 120kV limit and was set up around the 100kN test frame as shown in the Figure 1. It also has a 0.5 mm focal spot size, self-rectifying thermionic X-ray tube with a beryllium window, 0.76 mm Beryllium window thickness, and 30 degree beam divergence. For radiation safety, a lead-lined box surrounded the grips and test assembly.

Figure 1. X-ray system and test frame

Procedures

Strength of unnotched laminates were obtained in order to compare the residual strength results and normalize the graphs. Fatigue testing was performed at 5 Hertz. Up to five specimens of each laminate were tested, one each at $R = -0.1$ (mostly in tension), $R = -10$ (mostly in compression), $R = -1$ (fully reversed), $R = -0.35$ (more in tension), $R = -3$ (more

in compression). An anti-buckling plate surrounded the coupon to prevent large-scale buckling of the coupon under compressive loading. The Teflon-coated anti-buckling plate carried no axial loading during testing, and is shown in the test frame in Figure 2. The bolts were tightened to approximately 2.8 N-m.

Figure 2. Anti-buckling fixture surrounding coupon in test frame

The x-ray procedure used Polaroid type 55 P/N sheet film with a voltage of 52kV, 3mA amperage, and 73 seconds of exposure. A zinc iodide solution was first applied to the inside surface of the hole and coupon free edges with a syringe. The solution consisted of 60g zinc iodide, 8mL water, 10mL isopropyl alcohol, and 6mL of Kodak PhotoFlow [6]. After waiting 5 minutes to allow the zinc iodide die penetrant to wick into the any damaged areas, the film was exposed and processed according to the manufacturer's specifications. Digital images were then made from the negative using a stereomicroscope. The negative was backlit, and with a digital camera attached to the microscope, the image was captured.

DAMAGE INITIATION CONCEPT

The damage initiation concept involved using an approach to look for stress levels where first detectable damage can be found after 50,000 cycles. Critical damage was arbitrarily defined as 1.27 cm under typical inspection methods. If the damage found at a certain stress level did not exceed this criterion, the maximum stress was raised approximately 34.5 MPa, and the specimen was reexamined after 50,000 cycles at this new loading. If the damage, usually longitudinal splitting, exceeded 1.27 cm, the test would continue to 1 million cycles to assess long-term damage growth. This concept gleaned the most information from each specimen, as comparisons could be drawn at numerous stress levels and cycle counts. Also, different design methodologies could utilize the information obtained, such as the maximum stress level at which no damage was detected or at what stress level the damage exceeds the defined critical damage. Upon completion of the fatigue cycling, each specimen's residual strength was determined. The damage length versus stress level is plotted as a way to compare damage onset stresses and growth as a function of lay-up, stress ratio.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following section displays the findings of this experiment and discusses the differences in performance between the three laminates. The main variables discussed include the layup, R ratio, stress level, and damage mechanisms witnessed during the testing.

Preliminary Testing

Preliminary testing was done at a constant stress level, in order to determine the accumulated damage as a function of cycles. Approximate 60-80% of the long-term (1 million cycles) damage occurs in the first 50,000 cycles. The next 950,000 cycles show relatively minimal crack growth. One conclusion drawn is that if the composite does not show damage in the first 50,000 cycles, it is highly unlikely it will damage long-term.

Also, longitudinal and transverse properties of all the laminates were determined from classical lamination theory after inputting the known ply properties. Using the acquired data, the stress concentrations for the open hole, according to Lekhnitskii [3], were

found from the equation: $K_T^\infty = 1 + \left[\left(\frac{E_{11}}{G_{12}} \right)^{1/2} - 2\nu_{12} + 2 \left(\frac{E_{11}}{E_{22}} \right)^{1/2} \right]^{1/2}$. For the 50/40/10,

the concentration factor was 3.12. For the 70/30 specimens, it was 3.48. Lastly, for the 80/20, it was 3.69.

Experimental Results

For each test run, the laminate was fatigued in accordance with the damage initiation concept (50,000 cycles at low stress levels, then incrementally raising the stress until the damage criterion was reached, followed by cycling to 1 million total cycles). For the different R ratios, plots of the damage will provide comparisons across laminates and stress levels, followed by in-situ radiography images.

Cyclic Open Hole Tension

The first set of fatigue tests involved cycling that was mostly performed in tension, with $R = -0.1$ (a 10% reversal of loading into compression). Figure 3 show the stress at which damage initiates (intersection with x-axis), as well as the stress at which the critical damage criterion is exceeded. For all tests, the dominant mode of damage was splitting on the left and right side of the hole, in the longitudinal direction. This is typical for “hard” composite laminates. Stress concentrations around the notch were the reason damage consistently initiated at these sites. The long-term crack growth, from continued cycling at the highest stress level attained, is designated by the vertical portion of the line segment. Data is normalized to static ultimate strength in tension. In these tests, the traditional 50/40/10 laminate withstood a slightly higher absolute stress (data normalized to static ultimate strength). The 80/20 specimen and 50/40/10 specimen each exhibited a similar amount of long-term crack growth after the damage criterion was met. Figure 4 shows the different splits occurring in each laminate. With the non-traditional laminates (80/20 and 70/30), the split crack tips in different

longitudinal plies ($+5^\circ$ and -5° orientations) diverge as the cracks propagates, providing increased resistance to further damage as the splits extend in the longitudinal direction.

Figure 3. Open Hole Tension (OHT) tests (Specimen, Layup, Test type, R ratio)

Figure 4. Radiographic images around 6.35mm diameter notch after 1 million cycles at max stress in Open Hole Tension for a) 50/40/10 laminate, b) 80/20 laminate, and c) 70/30 laminate.

Cyclic Open Hole Compression

The second set of testing included fatigue testing the specimen mostly in compression, with $R = -10$ (10% reversal into tension). Figure 5 shows the corresponding split growth data acquired at each stress level. As before, stress levels for damage initiation and those required for surpassing the damage criterion of 1.27 cm are clearly evident. Data is normalized to static ultimate strength in compression for each layup.

Figure 5. Open Hole Compression (OHC) tests (Specimen, Layup, Test type, R ratio)

In compression, the 80/20 and 70/30 non-traditional laminates outperformed the typical 50/40/10 configuration by both withstanding a higher stress level and showing a slower long-term crack growth. Figure 6 shows the final damage state of each laminate upon completion of the fatigue testing.

Figure 6. Radiographic images around 6.35mm diameter notch after 1 million cycles at max stress in Open Hole Compression for a) 50/40/10 laminate, b) 80/20 laminate, and c) 70/30 laminate.

Cyclic Open Hole Fully Reversed

Fully Reversed fatigue testing, where $R = -1$ (equal stresses in tension and compression), separated the traditional and non-traditional laminates. Figure 7 compares the length of the longitudinal splitting across the different specimens. The data is normalized to the static ultimate tensile strength of the 50/40/10 composite laminate. The 80/20 and 70/30 laminates behaved almost identically, while the 50/40/10 consistently had less damage at the same stress level and was able to surpass the maximum stress achieved (before reaching the 1.27cm or 0.50" criteria) in the non-traditional laminates.

Figure 7 Open Hole Fully Reversed tests (Specimen, Layup, Test type, R ratio)

The final damage state of each laminate is shown in Figure 8. The 50/40/10 has very defined splits, corresponding to the cracks in individual plies being aligned with one another. The non-traditional ones show divergent crack paths as the splits lengthen.

Figure 8 Radiographic images around 6.35mm diameter notch after 1 million cycles at max stress Open Hole Fully Reversed for a) 50/40/10 laminate, b) 80/20 laminate, and c) 70/30 laminate.

Cyclic Testing for 50/40/10 Traditional Laminate

Comparisons within laminates show the effect of R ratios on the composite's performance. In direct contrast to metals, composites generally perform better in tension than in compression due to issues specific to that material system – namely microbuckling and kink banding [4]. Consequently, Open Hole Tension specimens withstood higher stresses before showing the same damage state as Open Hole Compression laminates at lower fatigue stresses. Figure 9 shows the five different tests run for the 50/40/10 laminate. For a fair comparison, both data sets are normalized to the static ultimate tensile strength of this layup, as the compressive strength is approximately half of the tensile strength and could be misleading. The tensile specimen withstood a 33% higher absolute maximum stress. In terms of maximum stress achieved, the ranking from best to worst was as follows: R = -0.1 (mostly in tension), R= -0.35 (more in tension), R=-10 (mostly in compression), R= -3 (more in compression), R= -1 (fully reversed).

Figure 9. 50/40/10 laminate tests (Specimen, Layup, Test type, R ratio)

Cyclic Testing for 80/20 Non-Traditional Laminate

The non-traditional laminate with 80% longitudinal plies ($\pm 5^\circ$), also exhibited the same trends when comparing across different R ratios as shown in Figure 10. In this case, there was a 16% increase in maximum absolute stress for the tensile specimen as compared to the compressive one. While the tensile specimen initiated damage first, it reached a higher stress. The long-term fatigue damage growth rate was almost identical. Also, the R = -0.35 tension specimen outperformed the R = -3 and R = -1 tests.

Figure 10. 80/20 laminate tests (Specimen, Layup, Test type, R ratio)

Cyclic Testing for 70/30 Non-Traditional Laminate

Comparing the tests for the non-traditional laminate with 70% longitudinal plies ($\pm 5^\circ$), a 17% increase in maximum stress was recorded for the Open Hole Tension test compared to its compressive test counterpart as displayed in Figure 11. While the tensile specimen initiates damage at a lower stress level, its growth is slower than the compressive test, and consequently reaches a higher stress level before split reaches the critical length of 1.27cm. The maximum stress achieved for the Fully Reversed test was approximately half of the value for the R = -0.1 tension test.

Figure 11. 70/30 laminate tests (Specimen, Layup, Test type, R ratio)

Discussion

The following section discusses the effects of the variables in this test matrix – specifically the type of layup, R values (stress ratios), stress levels, and damage mechanisms.

Type of Layup

The effects of the layup were significant, even at relatively short split lengths. Between the two non-traditional layups, the one with 80% longitudinal plies (80/20) had shorter split lengths at the same stress level than the 70/30 layup. When normalized to their own static ultimate strength, the 70/30 specimen withstood a higher percentage of its ultimate stress before the damage criterion of 1.27cm signaled the start of the long-term crack growth portion of the test.

Comparing the traditional layup with the non-traditional, the traditional outperformed the other two in tension, but was the worst in compression. The slightly off-axis plies are not as stiff as 0° plies, and could be susceptible to a scissor-like action that slightly tries to align them under tension. Under compression, there is no mechanism that would match this behavior. Even at small splits, the off-axis plies appear to stabilize the crack growth. At longer splits and under higher stresses, this effect would be amplified.

R values and stress levels

The stress ratios, R values, played a significant role in determining the highest stress level a composite specimen could handle without reaching the damage criterion that represented critical damage. Since composites have less damage modes affecting them in tension than in compression, stress ratios with greater percentages of tension during the fatigue cycle performed better. At the same stress level, the compression test laminates displayed a longer crack length. At longer crack lengths, the tension laminates could withstand a higher stress level.

CONCLUSION

Two non-traditional carbon fiber composite laminates ($[\pm 5/65/(\pm 5)_2/-65/\pm 5]_s$ and $[\pm 5/65/(\pm 5)_2/-65/5/65]_s$) were compared with a more traditional composite laminate

([45/90/-45/0₂/45/0₂/-45/0]_s) Their damage states were assessed through the use of in-situ radiography at predetermined intervals. Varying the stress ratio and stress level lent insight into finding the stress level for damage initiation and stress required for a 1.27cm long damaged area. The calculated stress concentrations, from the Lekhnitskii equation, were not able to predict which laminate would withstand the highest loading. For Cyclic Open Hole Tension, the traditional laminate slightly outperformed the traditional laminates by reaching a higher stress level before accumulating a critical damage. For Cyclic Open Hole Compression, the non-traditional laminates were the best at suppressing damage under fatigue loading. For Fully Reversed testing, the 80/20 laminate showed a distinct advantage at all stress levels over the other two. Within each laminate, comparing predominantly tension cycling with mostly compression cycling, the tension tests allowed the composite to reach a higher maximum absolute stress level. However, damage usually initiated in the tension specimen first, but had a slower growth rate.

Non-traditional laminates show promise for specific applications, specifically those that are compression dominated. Composite design requires a careful balance of different properties. A slight loss in stiffness due to off-axis plies might be offset by a higher damage tolerance that arrests cracks beyond a certain length.

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